

TERMINOLOGY

Error and Other Message Dialogs

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Foreword to the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative

The following document has been developed by the Error Messages Working Group of the Radiation Oncology Safety Stakeholder's Initiative (RO-SSI). The goal of the stakeholders group is to improve patient safety in radiation oncology. The RO-SSI meets twice a year (at the AAPM and ASTRO Annual Meetings). These meetings are attended by therapists, dosimetrists, medical physicists, biomedical and software engineers, clinical application experts, physicians, and therapy product manufacturers' experts. The attendees are affiliated with hospital-based or freestanding radiation therapy departments, radiation therapy product manufacturers, regulatory agencies, independent physician and physicist practices as well as manufacturers' associations, professional associations and societies.

The purpose of the Safety Stakeholder's Initiative is to combine the expertise of all stakeholders to identify opportunities for improving patient safety in all aspects of the radiation therapy treatment process. The RO-SSI, which is independent from all other organizations, develops recommendations for consideration by the various entities with

responsibilities for all or part of the radiation therapy treatment process.

In order to focus on various phases, functions and areas of the treatment process, the RO-SSI has organized several Working Groups (WGs) to concentrate on particular issues and eventually prepare recommendations. The recommendations represent the consensus of the members of the working groups. It should be noted that members of the working groups are individual expert contributors and their consent to a recommendation does not necessarily represent the endorsement of their employers.

The intent of the RO-SSI is to advise and suggest rather than prescribe actions or processes. It is hoped that the various organizations and societies with authority and responsibility in radiation oncology will consider the initiative's recommendations as they impact the respective roles of the existing organizations. Organizations which agree with RO-SSI recommendations will be able to post their support for the document as well as implement its use in their own environments. Through this open and transparent process, all radiation oncology professionals will have the opportunity to recognize and make use of the recommendations which have been developed by this unique and independent group of vendors, clinical users and other stakeholders.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

Currently, when clinicians read messages, they are often confused about the meaning, severity and next steps.

GUIDELINES

Vendors need to standardize message types, severity and icon attributes used for radiotherapy messages, both in software and for labeling of devices. The following table provides an overview of the types of software messages, sorted by message type and severity. For each, we provide one or more suggested examples of icons that should be used to label this type of message for clarity.

Message Type	Definition	Severity	Icon Example	Message Examples	Next steps
Error	<u>A problem has occurred</u> which stops the current operation, either by user action or system operation.	Critical		Stops the operation completely. Connectivity is down, or system is down.	User must restart the operation/application. May need to check for loss of information
		Non Critical	 Displaying an icon is optional for this type of message.	Minor user input error. "The number must be between 1 and 1,000.	The input error must be corrected before continuation of operation.
Warning	<u>A condition that might cause a problem</u> or harm if corrective actions are not taken.	Critical The problem is irreversible or it is likely to cause harm to patient, staff, or equipment.	 (ISO 7010-W001)	An over-ride has taken place which could cause harm if not warranted.	User must validate the current conditions before proceeding to the next step in the process to avoid harm.
		Non Critical, not likely to cause harm to patient, staff, or equipment. With correction, the potential problem can be averted.	 Displaying an icon is optional for this type of message.	User missed a step in the process. May not require a correction immediately.	User should evaluate the current conditions and determine if a correction is required.

Informational	Useful notifications.	None		Standby state, connection to the OIS made, imager arms are down,	User should read and understand the notification. Action may be required.
Completion	System provides feedback to the user communicating successful task completion.	None		Treatment complete.	User gets feedback from the system that operations are nominal.